

ROLE OF INTERNATIONALISMS IN ENGLISH-UZBEK LANGUAGE CONTACTS

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Abstract: The article talks about globalization and how all languages interrelate with others that results in borrowed elements of other languages. Language contact is being described and discussed as linguistic phenomenon. The article also looks into international words of English origin, their etymology and assimilation, their role in the development of English-Uzbek language contacts.

Key words: Language contacts, English, Russian, Uzbek, borrowings, international words, assimilation

Entrance of borrowed elements to the vocabulary of a certain language depends upon the history of a recipient language, being conditioned by direct linguistic contacts and political, economic, diplomatic and cultural ties between nations. In linguistics and scientific literature the terms “borrowed words” and “loan-words” are used as synonyms. Today in the globalization world all languages interrelate with each other which results in the fact that they can influence the pronunciation, vocabulary, writing and other aspects of the contacting languages. Uzbek language also was under the influence of Arabic, Persian, Russian and other languages during its historical development.

Thousands of words were borrowed from those languages, and borrowing became one of the most productive ways of enriching vocabulary. The latest research deeper study borrowings and divide them into following groups: exotic words, barbarisms, internationalisms, foreign inclusions, calques. Among other types of borrowings of English origin internationalisms or international words play an important role in the development of English-Uzbek language contacts. Language contact is the social and linguistic phenomenon by which users of different languages (or different dialects of the same language) interact with one another, leading to a transfer of linguistic features. Contact may occur between languages which are genetically related or unrelated, speakers may have similar or vastly different social structures, and patterns of multilingualism may also vary greatly. The development of the contacts between nations and the dominance of English language in the globalization era caused borrowing of some lexical units into Uzbek. The penetration history of English borrowings into Uzbek dates back to the end of XIX century and the beginning of the XX century. There are three main periods of penetration of English borrowings that can be observed:

1. Before the Great October revolution;
2. Soviet period;
3. Independence period.

Monographic research dedicated to study the history of English borrowings in Uzbek is scarce. The English borrowings are partially described by Borovkov, Mirzaev, Pulatov, Doniyorov and some others. Most of them included English borrowings in the group of Russian-international words and their research prove that the English words came into Uzbek through Russian.

In linguistics, an internationalism or international word is a loanword that occurs in several languages (that is, translingually) with the same or at least similar meaning and etymology. During the first period of English borrowings penetration only a few words came to Uzbek through Russian, most of which were exotic words: *миля* [Engl. mile], *фут* [Engl. foot], *МИТИНГ* [Engl. meet-ing], *вокзал* [Engl. Vauxhall], *доллар* [Engl. dollar], *тоннел* [Engl. tunnel] and others.

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During the Soviet period hundreds of English borrowings came into Uzbek through the Russian: джут [Engl.jute], трактор [Engl. tractor], спорт [Engl. sport], теннис [Engl.tennis], бизнес [Engl.business], фирма [Engl.firm] and many other international words.

At the end of XX century, especially, after the proclamation of Independence in Uzbekistan, many international words of English origin directly entered into Uzbek vocabulary in the result of language contacts. For example, дилер [Engl. dealer]; бизнес [Engl. distributor], брокер [Engl. broker]; бизнесмен [Engl. businessman]; бизнесвумен [Engl. businesswoman] and others. The study of international words existing in the vocabulary of Russian and Uzbek languages, aims to understand their modern conditions. Together with the synchronic studies of borrowings, diachronic studies dedicated to their etymology and dynamic are also important, in order to grasp full understanding of borrowings. According to the etymological principle (the possibility or impossibility of accurately establishing the time and source of borrowing, on the one hand, and the area of the word in the vocabulary of modern languages, on the other hand), all borrowed words belong to two groups: actually foreign borrowings and international vocabulary. Borrowings of English origin came to Uzbek in the result of English-Uzbek language contacts. The term “language contact” was forwarded first by Martine, and Weinreich and other scientists. The studies carried out on language contacts permit to set the traces of a certain word. In this article I look through some international words, which came from English into Uzbek directly or through other languages, which penetrated in the result of language contacts.

In the result of language contacts the quantity of English borrowings, especially, international lexicon raising day by day. It requires to develop new projects, dedicated to study anglicisms of the Uzbek, problems relation with the assimilation, compiling their lexicographic database in order to achieve efficiency in teaching English as a foreign language in Uzbekistan.

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